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Of Exclusive Victimhood and its Competitive Narratives in Post-Assad Syria

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Image 1: The city of Jableh on the Syrian coast witnessed extreme stress between Alawite and Sunni communities since December 8th, 2024. © Zoya Masoud, 2017.

In this contribution, I investigate continuities and ruptures across various patterns of exclusive victimhood in Assad- and post-Assad Syria. Having been born and spending the first 24 years of my life in Damascus, I witnessed the peaceful demonstrations that erupted in 2011, the subsequent outbreak of war in 2012, and its repercussions. Since 2015, I have conducted interviews with Syrians as part of my academic and professional work focusing on heritage destruction and how experiencing loss (re-)constitutes heritage and ascribes new values to it. These interviews contained testimonies about imprisonment and/or forced migration due to indiscriminate shelling and bombing and various forms of pervasive violence. After the euphoria over the Assad regime's collapse in December 2024 had faded in the wake of massacres against some Syrian communities, I witnessed some public responses of my earlier interviewees to these acts of violence. In the following, I invoke these two kinds of material to probe the possibility of imagining a practice that recognizes the extreme experiences of violence beyond attributing exclusive categories of victims and perpetrators to any certain group. I do this from a position of uncertainty, as events continue to accelerate and unfold.

Ruptures of the dictator-era

At the beginning of the peaceful demonstrations against the Assad regime in 2011, social media platforms became an arena for heated debate over the “truth” of what happened in Syria. Over nearly a decade and a half of an “infra-state conflict” (Vignal 2014), polarisation regarding the events

in Syria led to extreme segregation in the virtual sphere of social media: pro-Assad supporters unfriended/unfollowed those opposing him, and vice versa. Pro-Assad mass media outlets framed the peaceful demonstrators of 2011 as “sleeper-cells” of terror and “incubators” of terrorism, while the pro-revolution media channels portrayed it as a legitimate act of resistance against the repression policies of the Assad regime.

The regime had been implementing systematic and widespread violations against the Syrian population, including arbitrary detention, torture, enforced disappearances, and extrajudicial executions. International organisations such as the United Nations and Amnesty International characterise the Syrian war as a state of exception in which strategies such as “surrender or starve” have been implemented (Amnesty 2017, Daniels 2020).

The rebel areas inhabited by a Sunni majority were intensively bombed by the Assad government, supported by both the Russian army and Iranian and Lebanese Shi’a military forces (Alkousaa 2016, Graham-Harrison 2016, Grant & Kaussler 2019, Neumann & Schneider 2022). Various reports have interpreted the large-scale bombing by the Syrian-Russian coalition as a form of collective punishment (e.g., Vignal 2014, Clerc 2014, Sharp 2016, Abou Zainedin 2021). Individuals were exposed to constant fear of being murdered everywhere and at any time. Achille Mbembe names such a constellation of modern terror as “death-worlds;” namely “new and unique forms of social existence in which vast populations are subjected to living conditions that confer upon them the status of the *living dead*” (Mbembe 2016:92). Many Syrians fled the death-worlds and sought refuge in neighbouring countries, in Europe and the rest of the world.

After 14 years of war, a militia named Hay’at Tahrir al-Sham (HTS), supported by allied Turkish groups, led a coalition of military factions that on November 27, 2024, launched a military offensive campaign entitled “Deterrence of Aggression” against the Assad troops. The campaign was successful, and in the early morning on December 8, 2024, the fall of the Assad regime was officially announced, after Bashar al-Assad fled Damascus to Moscow, ending a 54-year-long dictatorial regime of the Assad family.

In a matter of hours, social and mass media were full of images and videos depicting the ongoing return of numerous refugees to Syria. Since then, and for the following weeks and months, many individuals I interviewed, who either remained in Syria throughout the war or returned after the fall of Assad for a visit, shared pictures of themselves in their cities on their social media profiles. Other visuals emerged documenting moments of liberating political prisoners from Assad’s torture-security centres, evoking a dual response: they are both horrifying and glorious visuals. The glory lies in the fact that individuals who endured captivity in dark underground prisons can now experience sunlight again. In contrast, the disturbing nature of the photographs from these facilities revealed the extreme conditions to which these prisoners were subjected. Each individual in Syria was exposed to the fear of entering such horror facilities. Those who were “living dead” in death-worlds before December 2024 got the chance after the collapse of the Assad dictatorship to speak out and articulate their experiences of injustice and get attention in the public sphere. The Assad regime not only marginalised their suffering but also stigmatised them as criminals and a risk to Syrian society.

Same slogans, different names

Before the collapse of the Assad regime, slogans glorifying Assad and portraying him as the saviour of Syria took an extreme form of self-destruction. For example, “*al-Assad au la Ahad*” (Either Assad or no one); “*Al-Asad au Nahruq al-Balad*” (Either Assad or we will burn the country). In the final months of 2025, similar slogans referring to Al-Sharaa appeared from the region around Deir az-Zour, particularly from *al-Asha’er* (Bedouin groups). Some people displayed messages on their cars, “*al-Sharaa au Nahruq al-Zare*” (Either Al-Sharaa or we will burn the agricultural crops). These parallel

uses of wording and terminology seem neither coincidental nor accidental; rather, they represent a continuity of belief in the exclusive occupation of power.

Though the impact of war was drastic in all of Syria, Sunni majority rebel regions faced disproportionately higher levels of violence during the conflict compared to areas controlled by the regime or inhabited predominantly by minorities (as documented also by Mazur 2021). The mass media of the Assad regime did not record these acts of destruction and killing in rebel areas as crimes, but as collateral damage of dismantling the danger from terrorists. While the regime categorized its own casualties as “shahid” (martyrs), it designated those who fell from the opposing side of rebels as terrorists. This oppressive pattern of collective punishments especially against certain rebel areas and of denial of victimhood for the Syrians living in these areas was arguably linked with a systematic instrumentalization of minority protection as a tool to consolidate the authoritarian regime’s power in Syria. Also, before 2011, the Assads portrayed any alternative to their rule as a direct road to sectarian chaos. Especially after they successfully suppressed Sunni Islamist opposition of the Muslim Brotherhood in the 1970s and 1980s, they presented themselves as a bulwark against Islamists who would persecute religious and ethnic minorities if they came to power.

Propagating the image of Assad as the sole guarantor of security for Syria’s minorities – particularly Alawites, Christians (including Armenians, Assyrians), Druze, Ismailis, and others – did not reflect the reality. Many minority communities lived below the poverty line without proper infrastructure. Additionally, many of their male members were forced to serve the compulsory military service, where they often faced injury or death.

When the regime fell, assaults against Alawites were often dismissed by the transitional government as “individual cases,” but they escalated on March 7, 2025. Following attacks on the new security forces by armed Alawite Assad-loyalists, a systematic massacre of Alawite communities began on that date. Human Rights Watch reported on identity-based killings against Alawites (2025). Records reported around 1400 victims (UN News 2025), with probably a greater number of undocumented cases. Since then, reports of abducted Alawite Women and girls frequently emerged. The perpetrators, many of whom belonged to the Ministry of Defence of the al-Sharaa government or to militias allied with it, filmed themselves and proudly posted evidence of their crimes (Reuters 2025). There have been reports of forced migration, eviction from homes and villages and the prevention of these communities from returning to their property (Syrians for Truth and Justice 2026).

Until now, the government’s response to the abduction and sexual enslavement has been limited to publishing a belated report by the Ministry of Interior that claims to record only 42 suspicious cases of abduction. However, the report found that 41 of the 42 suspicious cases were falsified or incorrect, and that only one abduction case was proven. No further details around the only one abduction were mentioned (see the Enab Baladi report on the investigation of Ministry of Interior, Syrian National News 2025).

As the Assad regime forcibly displaced Syrians, there are reports about a new practice of evicting Alawite families from their houses. For example, there was a mass forced displacement of predominantly Alawite villages in the eastern rural areas of Hama. Villages like *al-Zughbah*, *Muraywid*, *al-Talisyah*, *Ma’am*, *al-Faam* and *Abu Mansaf* were directly attacked following the collapse of the Assad regime on the 8th of December 2024 (Syrians for Truth and Justice 2026). Though the scale of displacement might have been greater during the Assad era against Sunni communities, it is still an unethical vantage point to accept evicting families from their houses due to their sectarian identity.

The mass media under Assad labelled peaceful demonstrators as “infiltrators” (*mundassūn*), or “revenge seekers” (*Mawtwrūn*) and ascribed political opponents of Assad to be “terrorists” and

“criminals.” Then, many families suffered the fateful disappearance of family members and watched them later on Syrian Television, admitting their participation in terrorist attacks on governmental facilities. These confessions were extracted from the victims under torture in Assad’s security centres. After Al-Sharaa came to power, the abduction of Alawite girls and women became increasingly common. Over time, more families began to raise their voices about the whereabouts of their daughters. Some female victims of sexual violence returned to their families and appeared in videos broadcast on social media accounts of the official Syrian TV channels. These videos were produced under obscure circumstances and aimed to systematically negate and deny the reality of the females’ abduction. The explanations given for their disappearance were trivial and nearly impossible to believe: visiting a friend in another city, forgetting to inform their family; finding a job in a faraway city and travelling there without giving notice to their relatives; experiencing family stress, or having fallen in love with another man, leaving their husband and kids behind without any note of their decision. One should keep in mind that Syrian society, and the Alawite community from cities and villages in the coastal area, is conservative and considers such behaviour of females to be unacceptable. Here, too, the practice of extracting fake confessions is repeated in both the Assad and Al-Sharaa eras.

The amount of discrediting directed at Alawite victims on social media and intergovernmental mass media shows a pattern of discrimination against these women, stripping them of their rights to be heard and believed. Such videos of Alawite females explaining their disappearances to be voluntary or forced due to family stress and not abduction are omnipresent on social media. I prefer not to quote these stories and reproduce their violence. For documented cases of unpublished cases, see the work and summary of the campaign’s documentation on cases of women’s abduction in Syria (February–December 2025) of the grassroots campaign “Stop the Abduction Of Syrian Women” in English and Arabic on their social media page, and the reports on the website of the Syrian Feminist Lobby (2025, 2026).

Exclusive victimhood

Since the beginning of 2025, my social media feeds have been filled with testimonies and news of horrifying incidents of sexual violence. Posts from friends of friends in the cities and villages where my aunts and cousins live – the same places where I spent my childhood vacations at my grandmothers’ and relatives’ houses on the Syrian coast – have been particularly unsettling. Social media also played a crucial role in shaping narratives around these events, with many blaming the victims due to their alleged ties to the former regime. The acceleration of events was accompanied by waves of amplified polarisation and campaigns that oversimplified complex issues on social media, resulting in effects with global repercussions. Syrians around the globe participated in such debates. Some individuals, whom I interviewed for my research before the fall of Assad, expressed discriminatory views against Alawite victims and shared pejorative jokes about Alawite women, suggesting they were disloyal to their men, hence blaming the victims for the sexual violence imposed on them. Even some of my female interlocutors engaged in such social media discourses.

In this contribution, I will share insights on two patterns of my former interviewees and their reactions to the violence against Alawite women. There are other patterns within my interview samples, supporting Alawite victims. However, this contribution focuses only on these two patterns.

The first group did not actively celebrate the violent events but rather focused on celebrating the achievements of the interim government without mentioning the atrocities committed against the Alawite communities. For instance, they celebrated an agreement between the interim Syrian president Ahmad al-Sharaa and Mazlum Ibadi, the leader of the Syrian Democratic Forces (SDF), which was signed on March 10, even as attacks on Alawites were still unfolding. This agreement

promised to affirm the inclusion of Kurds in the political transition process and guaranteed their rights and interests. Some interviewees posted about this but failed to mention war crimes against the Alawites. During the Assad era, members of this same group of interviewees accused any Syrian who did not openly condemn the regime's criminal acts of complicity and indirect participation in causing their suffering. Nevertheless, in March 2025, they themselves ignored the suffering of Alawites.

The second group of my interviewees did not remain silent; but engaged with the news about the massacre, responding with the "haha" emoji and claiming that the victims were adopting a fake "mazlumiyya" (oppression position). According to them, Alawites were misusing and abusing their victimhood to undermine what the people posting perceived to be a fair and just interim government of Syria. They labelled anyone who shared information about sexual violence or the murder of Alawites as "fulul" (remnants of the Assad regime). The landscape on social media became extremely polarised.

Many of my interviewees before December 2024 experienced the horror of the death-worlds and stepped out of their previous home cities, traumatised with scars on their personal biographies. Following the downfall of the Assad regime, however, these individuals, who had been denied their rights to representation, experienced a moment of recognition. Those who were defeated and denied their civil rights of freedom of speech and were either forcibly displaced or imprisoned under the Assad era, celebrated what they considered a victory after the fall of the Assad dictatorship. Nevertheless, they also managed to deny or justify the crimes against the Alawite communities in post-Assad Syria.

The cluster of social media reactions around the Alawite massacres showed that some of these interviewees internalised the dominant discourse of the interim government and aimed to be virtual defenders of Ahmad al-Sharaa in a dogmatic attitude, denying the pain of others.

Al-Sharaa's government is thus establishing a hegemonic discourse that mirrors that of Assad, marginalising the sufferers of certain groups, while framing the suffering of its own group as singular, unique, incomparable, or morally superior. This approach comes at the expense of acknowledging harm to others. By introducing competitive narratives of suffering, the government positions its own persecution as the only legitimate one, delegitimising other narratives and framing victimhood as bound solely to its social groups of allies. This transforms suffering into a political category to be instrumentalised to justify own committed crimes, rather than acknowledging it as a universal human experience. Within post-conflict communities worldwide, these transformations have been a recurring theme (see Druliolle and Brett 2019). Institutionalising such exclusive spaces also means consolidating them through commemorative practices. For example, certain Syrians posted pictures of humiliations of Alawites on social media on the first anniversary of the massacres against Alawites in March 2025. Some even indicated that the 7th of March 2025 was an "extension of the revolution," as one post put it.

The interim government aims to capitalise on and appropriate the trauma of the death-worlds, which Syrians went through in a single cast that aligns with its objectives, namely, a trauma or persecution of Sunni communities, which the new regime argues was inflicted mainly by the Alawite minority. In doing so, the new government downplays or mitigates the suffering of Alawite individuals under its reign and frames the atrocities against them as fragmented and as a quest for rightful revenge against a perpetrator. This sense of exclusive victimhood stems from the intensity of suffering and its temporality. One interlocutor captured this sentiment by saying, "We suffered first." This quote reflects the broader tendency recorded in several excerpts. In an interview on the official Syrian TV, a narrative of disproportion between Sunni and Alawite perpetrators was propagated (Syrian National

News 2025). Even if we entertain the concept of accusing all perpetrators of atrocities in the Assad era of being Alawite, this still does not justify attacking civilian Alawite women and abducting them, nor does it justify assassinating Alawite perpetrators. The latter must be brought before the court and held accountable for their crimes. The instrumentalizing or manipulation of one social group's victimhood to legitimise or justify further violence, are evident here.

But what constitutes Sunni trauma? Many victims of the Assad regime, who were born to Sunni families, are advocating for Alawite victims. Some of those celebrating the sectarian atrocities remained silent during the Assad era, especially the ones who stayed in Syria and did not flee the war. These latter individuals did not lend their support to Assad's victims regardless of their sect and ethnic backgrounds. Jeffrey C. Alexander (2012) defines collective traumas in his social study as "reflections of neither individual suffering nor actual events, but symbolic rendering that constructs and imagines them." The ambiguity of mental images on trauma resulted after the Assad era played the role of an incubator for spacing processes, assigning all Alawites as perpetrators, and all Sunnis as victims. These claimed homogenous groups have never existed as such in the Syrian society: some Sunni elite actors cooperated with the regime, and some Alawites opposed the regime and vice versa. Here, trauma appears to be not only socially constructed, but also fails to resonate with any holistic, alleged homogenous group of Syria.

In a post-dictatorship Syrian setting, implicit or explicit comparisons of suffering treat recognition as a scarce resource rather than a shared moral and ethical obligation. This reproduces the Assad regime's mechanisms for treating individuals and groups unevenly based on their sect, political, and ethnic affiliations, and definitely reproduces the exclusive patterns of binary thinking: those "good" citizens loyal to the interim government against those "bad" citizens who oppose it.

Of multidirectionality

The primary issue with such a competitive narrative is its drastic effects on civic identity and a sense of belonging in post-Assad Syria. Michael Rothberg (2009) introduced the concept of multidirectional memory, going beyond competitive memory. This invites us to promote multivocality and plurality in our thinking of identity's discourses. It is essential to create a representational space that encompasses all human communities that have historically inhabited the geographical territory known as Syria. To truly celebrate our plurality and diversity, rather than suppressing it under the dominant narratives of majorities and minorities, we must actively engage economically, politically, and socially marginalised groups in public discourse. These groups should be empowered to articulate their suffering, their rights to the city, village, heritage, and express their identities.

When marginalised populations, who often lack representation in official discourses, raise their voices through narratives that reflect their histories and heritage, they challenge the prevailing interpretive systems that govern societal discourse. By elucidating their demands for safety, justice, and dignity, both spatially and socially, they play a crucial role in shaping the conversation around governance.

Interim governments should be held accountable for refining the discourse surrounding a unified Syrian national identity by emphasising the pluralism inherent in historical narratives. This entails fostering democratic spaces that facilitate the representation of diverse identities within the public sphere. Achieving fair and democratic representation necessitates ongoing negotiation and dialogue regarding the foundations and narratives of these identities, alongside a commitment to honouring the lived experiences of all citizens. This is particularly crucial given Syria's complex and painful legacy of 54 years under dictatorship and violent repression.

The painful stories of those affected by this tumultuous history must not be overlooked, as they are integral to understanding the social fabric of contemporary Syria. Integrating and acknowledging the

experiences of all individuals and communities identifying as Syrian can foster chains of solidarity and mutual support. This approach promises to assist in the sustainable reconciliation and enhance social relationships among Syrians.

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